

THE NEEDS FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS' AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES – AS A KEY FACTOR TO BOOST LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The new world has introduced new demands and different challenges to deal with to every member of the society. This can be encountered in the world of teaching EFL/ESL classes as well. For example, today's young and adolescent learners are becoming more dependent on the teacher, while the need is to enhance more inductive and student-centered learning behaviour. According to the results of reviewing different works by prominent scientists, today's teachers have two obligations: one, they should integrate more students – centered atmosphere in EFL classes, the second is that they should motivate language learners to be more autonomous in their learning process. In the below paragraphs, the broad explanation and review of a few scientific works are analyzed and went to a clear results and recommendations for language teachers.*

Keywords: *autonomous learners, dependency, learning habits, inductive teaching.*

НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ – КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ФАКТОР ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *Новый мир предъявил новые требования и различные проблемы, с которыми приходится сталкиваться каждому члену общества. С этим можно столкнуться и в мире преподавания классов EFL/ESL. Например, сегодняшние учащиеся младшего и подросткового возраста становятся все более зависимыми от учителя, в то время как необходимо повышать более индуктивное и ориентированное на ученика поведение в обучении. Согласно результатам обзора различных работ выдающихся ученых, у современных учителей есть две обязанности: во-первых, они должны интегрировать больше студенческо-ориентированной атмосферы в занятия EFL, во-вторых, они должны мотивировать изучающих язык быть более автономными в своем учебном процессе. . В приведенных ниже абзацах проанализировано широкое объяснение и обзор нескольких научных работ, которые привели к четким результатам и рекомендациям для учителей иностранных языков.*

Ключевые слова: *автономные учащиеся, зависимость, учебные привычки, индуктивное обучение.*

INTRODUCTION

In the era of technology and internet, every single field of the world is developing fast and doesn't match to the pace of yesterday's plan and framework of living. In this kind of situation, the teaching sphere is also being influenced and several new demands and needs are appearing. In order to address these demands it is demanded from the educators, including EFL/ESL instructors to integrate new approaches, innovative methods and constructive techniques into their teaching classes. What are some examples of these methods or techniques? It is stated by Little A. that one of the most constructive way of teaching which can fulfill the demands of contemporary world is setting up more students-centered classroom management in EFL classes [1], in other words, we as language instructors should let students to be more

independent and autonomus rather than being dependent to the teacher and immitators of the language instructors. One of the main reason or this conception is that new society aren't interested in obeyfull and limeted cadres, new society don't tend to accept mentally isolated learners. Those people who are improving and getting more colourfull results in their working and studying career are the people who have own perceptions and separate way of acting in the filed that they are living and working.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are several scientific researchers who did a significant work in improving learners autonomy and independancy in order to inhance their foreign language learning process. On the top of these researchers' list is Dang T. who claimed that Learner autonomy has been identified as a complicated capacity that potentially has a great impact on personal growth and achievement [2]. By this, he drew the attention of the EFL teachers that letting the language learners be more independent leads them not only being successful in language classes and in their language capacity but also in their personal life and in their achievements. If we consider that teaching is not only consist of teaching language but it includes didactics which shares the obligation of building a well-behaviour of the learners, it is a good way of teaching.

RESULTS

Furthermore, another author of the same field works – Lamb classified how can it be seen the learners autonomy in language classes. According to him it can be seen mainly on freedom of choice and the opportunity of negotiation and creating free atmosphere in language classes [3]. From this perception, it can be understood that the way in which the language teachers can boost learners autonomy and make them more successful and constructive is in the opportunity of having free choices from the language learners. Free choices should be received by learners in choosing their way of learning, timing and focusing skills [4]. One of the main reason for giving choices in these fields that learners more stronger and broader notion of how they can learner better, when they can learn better and what are some kills of language that they should focus on more as they have clear idea of for what purposes will they use the target language. Another scientist Pipit M. connects learners autonomy with special conditions. He claims that the coronovirus lockdowns enabled to the language learners to be more autonomus [5]. Not only enabled, but also it was the demand of the time. As most of the educational centres and teaching instutions were locked down and majority of the teaching process were conducting in online mode and this creates to the students more autonomus atmosphere where they should care about their learning process mainly by themselves. This condition also helped to thousands of language learners to understand the importance of self study. They were able to see how they can improve and flourish in their language learning process with self study rather than obeying andimmitating to the teachers orders and instructions. Other scientists such as Allameh T. implies that there are some criteria for language learners to be autonomus and to be successful in this mode of learning. For example, they should understand the nature of learning process, they should understand what to do and how to control the language learning process in order to be more effective language learner [6].

DISCUSSION

There are several different approaches in the literature which are devoted to the perspectives of language learning autonomy. The main issue of exploring and defining the term is about how to connect this idea to the philosophy and main concept of implementing the

autonomy to the language learning classes. For example, some of the scientists who are working in the field are offering to analyze and accept the learners' autonomy concept from positive, negative and constructive aspects while others are connecting this idea from teachers and students perspectives. In order to comprehend this notion, we should understand the idea of perspective which deals with all the identity and central notions of one learner about how to learn, study and gain the language in the easy and appropriate way for themselves. At the same time, the learners who wants to find their own appropriate way to learn the new information should be ready to overcome some obstacles which can be appeared in front of their way to success. On of them is the controversion for the teachers. As everybody knows, many teachers at various educational institutions such as schools, lyceums even higher educations tend to implement their system, their autonomy in learning process. And they don't like students to be independent from their regime and be independent. In these cases students should address some more barriers in their autonomy learning process.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, the idea pf being autonomy in language learning process is not a simple concept. In order to achieve any success learners should deal with some barriers and be more target-oriented in their learning process.

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